

THE PROBLEM OF IMPROVING GRAMMATICAL COMPETENCE IN THE WORKS OF UZBEK RESEARCHERS: BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

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Abstract. *The article is aimed at studying the effectiveness of various methods of teaching grammar analyzed in the works of Uzbek researchers, which will not only identify the most successful practices, but also offer recommendations for teachers working in the field of teaching foreign languages. Thus, this study has both theoretical and practical significance, contributing to improving the quality of teaching foreign languages in education organizations.*

Keywords: *education, foreign language, method, approach, practice, communicative competence, grammar, student, teacher.*

Teaching English grammar is an important aspect in the process of learning a foreign language, which requires special attention from teachers and methodologists. Grammar, as the basis of the language structure, plays a key role in the formation of communication skills, understanding and interpretation of texts, as well as in the development of critical thinking in students. In the context of globalization and rapid development of technology, knowledge of English is becoming not only necessary, but also relevant for successful professional activity and personal growth. In this regard, the study of the didactic aspects of teaching English grammar is of particular importance.

The problem of improving communicative competence in general and grammatical competence in particular in teaching foreign languages is a pressing issue, especially in the professional activities of Uzbek teachers and philological researchers. During the years of independence, many studies have been conducted in this area by domestic scientists. Among them, the methods of teaching foreign languages are studied by Jalolov J., Khoshimov U., Akhmedova L.T., Normuratova V.I., the role of various approaches (communicative approach, integrative approach, cluster approach) in teaching English has been studied by such researchers as Tadjibaev G.Sh., Gulyamova M.Kh., Kushieva N.Kh., the introduction of CEFR into the education system of Uzbekistan is considered in the works of Rashidova F.M. and Kulmatova B.G.; Mamyrbayeva D.D. conducted a study on the methods of teaching students the passive voice in English, Mustafayeva H.T. studied the linguistic and methodological features of teaching English grammar to students of the socio-humanitarian faculties. The measures taken in our country to improve foreign language education in the higher education system, the introduction of international standards in the educational process of universities have become the reason for the study of foreign languages, especially English, also by students who do not specialize in this area.

The development of foreign language communicative competence plays an important role not only in the activities of foreign language teachers or representatives of related fields in this area, but also in specialists from other professions, due to the ever-expanding scale of globalization and the increasing demands of the modern labor market. As early as the last century, scientists and

methodologists realized the need to choose a method or approach to teaching a foreign language based on the ultimate goal of the student, which resulted in the concept of "language for specific purposes". The purpose of studying a foreign language within this area varies depending on the student's specialty. However, as Kh. T. Mustafayeva notes, "this should not lead to the allocation of a separate language for each specialty ... the changes concern only the area of application of means of expression, linguistic units". This, in turn, requires careful selection of language material, especially grammatical material. Because, when teaching a foreign language to a student of a non-linguistic specialty, it is necessary to know which aspects of the language play an important role in this area and which topic can be studied superficially. For example, a future English teacher must know and be able to use all twelve tenses in the language, while a student in the technical field can exclude four or five of them, and the level of knowledge of English will be sufficient in future professional activities. So, within the framework of the system of English for specific purposes, "the preparation of educational material is aimed at selecting language units that can be used within the framework of a given specialty, and determining the subject and content of education". [4, 50] Therefore, this confirms our opinion that the organization of foreign language education in philological and non-philological faculties does not occur in the same way, which is especially evident in determining the content of education and the presentation of language material. The presentation of language material, within the framework of developing grammar skills, should be understood as both an explanation of the rules and the performance of exercises. The researcher, emphasizing the importance of conventional speech exercises, means by such exercises only exercises in translating texts [4, 65], which to date does not give the desired result. The method of text translation is aimed at developing reading and writing skills, with minimal attention to listening and speaking skills, which indicates an incomplete development of communicative competence, part of which is grammatical competence. That is why the translation method is considered a rather outdated method of teaching foreign language, which in the current conditions of rapidly developing technologies is used as a supplement to modern approaches and is used in most cases as an exercise for independent or extracurricular learning.

It should be noted that previously in the system of teaching foreign languages, the priority was the acquisition of theory and grammar with an insufficient level of communication skills. With the adoption of the CEFR requirements as a legal basis for teaching foreign languages in our country, special attention began to be paid to the personality-oriented and integrative approaches in the system of higher foreign language education. According to Gulyamova M.Kh., "integrated education, first of all, involves the unification, integration and comprehensive teaching of subjects that are close and compatible with each other". [2, 45] Here, it is necessary to emphasize the difference in the application of the integrative approach in teaching foreign language in philological and non-philological higher education institutions. In non-philological areas, a foreign language is taught in conjunction with specialized subjects, while in philological areas, the essence of the integrative approach lies in the uniform improvement of all speech skills. Focusing on the integrative approach, the researcher criticizes the teaching of such subjects as Reading, Writing, Communicative Normative Phonetics in the system of foreign language education, in which speech aspects are taught separately. [2, 59] However, in our opinion, this criticism is inappropriate due to the fact that there are also subjects in practical English and an integrated course of teaching foreign language, which implies the development of all speech aspects within the framework of

one discipline. At the same time, classes on each type of communication skills create the basis for a deeper assimilation of the target language by future specialists in this field.

When teaching foreign language, one should not forget about the role of interference. “Transfer of communication skills from one language to another is a pressing issue in teaching foreign language. In this regard, language experience can hinder the implementation of newly acquired skills and competencies or facilitate this process. Negative influence, interference can occur within one language, i.e. in the foreign language itself, or between the native and foreign languages”. [1] Most researchers in teaching foreign language consider only linguistic interference, however, as noted by Professor Jalalov J.J., there are three types of interference in this area: language interference, cultural interference, and methodological interference. If language interference occurs at all levels of language, then cultural interference is divided into verbal and non-verbal. Methodological interference affects such methodological categories as learning conditions, learning goals, learning content, and learning methods. [3] Linguistic and cultural interference must be overcome by a foreign language student, while methodological interference creates difficulties for a foreign language teacher. Such a division of the concept of interference by scientists contributes to a comprehensive study of this concept in foreign language education and determines the study of this issue in a complex.

In general, teaching foreign language, in particular English, requires the development of effective pedagogical technologies that meet the modern requirements of foreign language education. The question of choosing traditional and non-traditional methods in this process remains open, but the connection of grammar with speech in improving linguistic skills is supported by many researchers. The analysis of scientific and methodological literature within the framework of this study showed that the improvement of grammar skills should occur in close connection with the improvement of communicative competence. The priority of one aspect of the language over another one leads either to a large number of errors in the written and oral speech of students, or to uncertainty and insufficient practice of communication in a foreign language.

Thus, teaching English is a complex process in which specialists, along with the problem of choosing a method or approach, also face the issue of integrating language skills, while overcoming interference. In this regard, the study of linguistic features of teaching foreign language grammar at all stages of language learning process remains an issue that requires a solution in the education system of our country.

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